

A Study of Job Performance among Banking Employees in North-East India

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 09 March 2019

Keywords

Banking sector, human resource management, human resource training, job performance.

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to examine, investigate and analyse the job performance among employees of banking industry. Job performance assesses the performance of the employees and the expected job output from every employees in the organisation. In this present business world, many business organisations are facing various challenges in balancing and maintaining the job performance, this resulted in the need for appropriate human resource management (HRM) in the organization. This study will help the organisation to know the importance of job performance as one of the human resource (HR) practices and generates the idea of various important HR aspects for achieving organisational goals. For the present study, a total number of ten banks in Manipur were selected. It is a descriptive study with fifty samples chosen using stratified random sampling. The self-prepared questionnaire was self-administered to the respondents. The study revealed that education has a significant difference in the job performance. HR training such as technical or technology training, quality training, life skills training, soft skills training and legal training will certainly improve the job performance.

1. Introduction

Job performance is an individual evaluation of employees on how well the work is done. It assesses whether the employees have done the job well or not. It also indicates the effectiveness of employees in performing and completing the given task with limited resources and within the given time. Job performance has a great impact on achieving organisational goal. It is of paramount importance for every individual to perform the job well and complete the assigned task within the given time. There are various factors that affect the performance of employees. In this present era of globalisation, the management and action of job performance is gradually becoming more difficult and it affects the multi-tasking in any organisation. In order to achieve organizational goal, the human resource (HR) department has given a continuous effort adopting new strategies in the organization. On the other hand, employees need to be more competent, innovative, flexible, and trained enough to handle the knowledge effectively.

In the banking sector employees with technical know-hows and skills are considered as vital assets as it supports the job performance which enhances the organisational productivity. As bank could be an industry, the services that bank provided are delivered to its customers through its employees and thus the services are consumed by its customers at the same time. Hence, the bank employees act as representatives of the standard and quality of their bank services to its clients (Aryee, 2009).

Job performance encompasses the employee's personality that contributes to the banking performance, it refers to actions that are a part of the formal reward system (i.e., technical core), and addresses the necessities as per job descriptions (Williams and Karau, 1991). At a general level, Job performance consists of activities which delineates into

products and services created by the organization or permits for economical functioning of the organization (Motowidlo et al., 1997). Thus, job performance covers the fulfilment of the necessities that are part of the contract between the leader and employee. Campbell et al., (1993) describes job performance as an individual-level variable, or something a single person does. This differentiates it from more encompassing constructs such as organizational performance or national performance, which are higher-level variables.

2. Review of Literature

Boxall & Purcell (2011) assert that HR management doubtlessly contributes to employee job performance within the organisation. The standard of employee job performance is dependent on performance ability, motivation and chance. This suggests HR managers intervene to develop employees' ability, motivation and chance so as to maximise job performance within the organisation. Motivation refers to external and internal factors that influence employees to perform a selected task or job well. One of the roles of HR managers is to maximise the extent of worker motivation. Wilton (2016) points out that it's necessary for HR managers to design jobs, implement practices, conduct procedures, and create an atmosphere conducive to stimulate and encourage workers to perform to their full potential within the means desired by the organisation. Human resource management (HRM) refers to the activities together with recruiting, work planning and coaching, developing, evaluation, guiding and motivating workers within the organization. HRM is "the framework of policies, and procedures and practices for managing the link between employers and employees" (Du Plessis, 2015). Nabet al., (2016) claimed that the outcome of HRM practices is absolutely and considerably related with job satisfaction. Job satisfaction retains the current employees and attracts the competent employees that relates to the upper productivity and organizational long term performances. On the

other hand HRM practice and job satisfaction are negatively related with absence and turnover. However, the results of HRM practice, Job performances and job satisfaction are negatively correlated with absence and turnover. Wherever Motivation is more, the performance level is additionally high. On the other hand employee participation and enjoying an energetic role in business area has a great significant impact on job satisfaction of the employees of Dhaka banks. Nadarajah et al., (2012) said that the job performance is often confused with effort which refers to energy expended whereas performance is a measurable aspect. Performance can be defined as the accomplishment of an employee's assigned duties and the outcomes generated on a specified job function or activity within a specified time period given. There is consensus that human capital is significant related to firm performance. Furthermore, there is a long list of high-performance HR practices that may affect the organizational performance. A growing body of empirical evidence, mainly originating from American studies, suggest that firms are increasingly incorporating high-performance HR practices in order to improve financial performance and to sustain the competitive advantage.

Paauwe & Richardson, (1997) the idea behind the belief that HRM considerably contributes to organisational results is that the HR practices affects the workers in a very positive matter, for example, in increasing job satisfaction and motivation, in improving the operational results, like the number and quality of the merchandise and services, that once more can have positive impact on the monetary and market performance of a corporation, like come back on assets, revenue, and market share. Hordos (2018) an entrepreneur might assume that job performance is only about how well employees perform their duties. However, job performance involves various factors. For example, you might expect a particular employee to add substantial value to your company because he's capable of performing his task at a high level. But "job performance" involves both "task performance" and "contextual performance." For example, a shoe salesperson's task performance is evaluated on how many pairs of sneakers, sandals or work boots she sells on average per day, week or month. Her contextual performance rates how well she gets along with co-workers and customers, how effectively she solves problems that affect the team or company and how she keeps busy during slow periods.

Sonnentag, Volmer & Spychala (2008) said that the major performance dimensions views individual performance as a multi-dimensional concept. At the most basic level, performance can be differentiated in terms of process and outcome. Moreover, one can distinguish between task, contextual, and adaptive performance and each of these types in itself is multidimensional. These performance types differ with respect to their antecedents and consequences and can be conceptually and empirically separated. Measurement of performance is central as important organizational decisions are based on individual performance. Athar & Shah (2015) revealed that training is one of the key element that help employees to gain knowledge and confer motivation and satisfaction. Training enhances skills and abilities of employees. Through training employee learn teamwork and

integrity. On the other hand, it also contributes positively towards development of employee performance along with other factor. Performance of the relationship depends on the worker responsibility which is to be determined by HR technique of the training and development. By giving additional training stages in the association workforce become involved to gain further information about their occupation which finally supports them in accomplishment of campaigns between their peer assemblies.

3. Methodology

The study was conducted in the state of Manipur, Northeast India. The objective of the study is to examine, investigate and analyse the job performance among employees of banking industry. Descriptive research design (Lal Das, 2007) is used in this study. Stratified random sampling is used to select fifty samples. The self-prepared questionnaire on job performance is a Likert rating scale with five responses viz, strongly agree (5), agree (4), neither agree nor disagree (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1) respectively. The scores are summated for the final analysis. In addition to the job performance questionnaire, socio-demographic is also used. The self-prepared questionnaire was given to the respondents and it was completed by the respondent themselves. The study is predominantly quantitative in nature. The research ethics are strictly adhered to during the collection of data. IBM SPSS 20.0 was used for data analysis. The cutoff score for job performance was calculated based on the recommendation of Singh (2006).

4. Research Hypothesis

- H1: There is a significance difference between the gender of the employees and their job performance
- H2: There is a significance difference between place of residence of the employees and their job performance
- H3: There is a significance difference between educational qualification of the employees and their job performance
- H4: There is a relationship between the age of the employees and their job performance
- H5: There is a relationship between income of the employees and their job performance
- H6: There is a significance difference between job orientation of the employees and their job performance
- H7: There is a relationship between the experience of the employees and their job performance
- H8: There is a significance difference between organisational name of the employees and their job performance
- H9: There is a significance difference between department's name of the employees and their job performance
- H10: There is a significance difference between the position of the employees and their job performance.

5. Data analysis

Socio-demographic Profile

- In this study, 66% are male and 34% are female.
- The average age of the respondents is 29.7 years, the average income (per month) is INR 11507 and the

- average work experience of the respondents is 5 years.
- 56% of the respondents are Christians and 40% are Hindus.
- Exactly half of the respondents are from urban areas.
- 74% of the respondents are in team based work.
- In this study 4 per cent have low job performance and 96 per cent have medium job performance.

Table 1: Independent sample t-Test between Respondent's Gender and Job Performance

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	df	Sig.
Job Performance	Male	33	60.85	10.99	-0.175	48	0.862
	Female	17	41.02	61.41			
	Total	50	50.935	36.2			

The difference between male (M = 60.85, SE = 1.794) and female (M = 61.41, SE = 2.826) was not significant in their job performance $t(48) = -.175, p > .05$. Hence, **H1₀** is accepted and

H1₁ is rejected. Therefore, there is no difference in the job performance of male and female bank employees.

Table 2: One –way ANOVA between Residence and Job Performance

Residence	N	Mean	SD	F value	Sig.
Urban	25	51.56	13.16	F = 1.585 df = 2, 47	0.216
Rural	16	47	13.2		
Others	9	47.33	12.43		
Total	50	48.66	12.79		

There is no significant difference between the place of residence of the respondent and their job performance, $F(2, 47) = 1.585, p > .05$. Hence, **H2₀** is accepted and **H2₁** is rejected.

Therefore, there is no difference in the job performance of employees residing in urban area with that of rural area.

Table 3: One –way ANOVA between respondents Educational Qualification and Job Performance

Education	N	Mean	SD	F value	Sig.
Graduate	28	59.46	10.03	F = 4.529 df = 2, 47	0.016
Post Graduate	19	60.74	10.25		
Diploma	3	77.67	5.77		
Total	50	61.04	10.67		

There is a significant difference between the educational qualification of the respondent and their job performance, $F(2, 47) = 4.529, p < .05$. Hence, **H3₀** is rejected and **H3₁** is accepted. Therefore, there is a difference in the job

performance of employees based on educational qualification. And the job performance of employees with diploma is higher than others.

Table 4: One –way Analysis between respondents Job Orientation and Job Performance

Job orientation	N	Mean	SD	F value	Sig.
Individual Based	4	61.5	14.06	F = .876 df = 2, 47	0.423
Team Based	37	59.97	10.83		
Others	9	65.22	8.38		
Total	50	61.04	10.67		

There is no significant difference between the job orientation of the respondent and their job performance, $F(2, 47) = .876, p > .05$. Hence, **H4₀** is accepted and **H4₁** is

rejected. Therefore, there is no difference in the job performance of the employees based on their job orientation.

Table 5: One –way ANOVA between respondents Organisation and Job Performance

Name of the Organization	N	Mean	SD	F value	Sig.
Axis	8	67.38	13.05	F = 1.828 df = 9, 40	0.093
IDBI	5	60.80	5.93		
SBI	12	53.75	11.24		

UCO	2	66.50	6.36		
UBI	5	67.20	10.23		
Bank of Baroda	3	54.00	7.00		
Canara	5	60.00	9.35		
Bandhan	3	56.33	6.66		
PNB	4	65.75	4.03		
CBI	3	67.00	9.54		
Total	50	61.04	10.67		

There is no significant difference between the name of the organisation of respondent and their job performance, $F(9, 40) = 1.828$, $p > .05$. Hence, H_{50} is accepted and H_{51} is

rejected. Therefore, there is no difference in the job performance of the employees based on the type of banks.

Table 6: One –way ANOVA between Department of the Respondents and Job Performance

Name of the Department	N	Mean	SD	F value	Sig.
Cash	6	60.33	13.32	F = 0.417 df = 15, 34	0.963
Retail Banking	3	57.00	9.17		
Account opening	2	67.50	19.09		
Customer service	7	61.86	7.65		
Finance	1	44.00	-		
General Banking	3	60.67	9.87		
Advance	3	60.33	17.93		
Credit	1	62.00	-		
Banking	8	59.63	13.36		
Loan	1	56.00	-		
Clerical	4	67.75	8.22		
Sales	2	60.00	2.83		
P.S.B	1	51.00	-		
Gold Loan	1	70.00	-		
Operation	6	61.83	11.30		
Recovery	1	66.00	-		
Total	50	61.04	10.67		

There is no significant difference between the department name of the respondent and their job performance, $F(15, 34) = .417$, $p > .05$. Hence, H_{60} is accepted and H_{61} is rejected.

Therefore, the job performance of the bank employees from all the departments are same.

Table 7: One –way ANOVA between Position of the Respondents and Job Performance

Name of the Position	N	Mean	SD	F value	Sig.
Assistant Manager	8	60.50	14.14	F = 2.111 df = 10, 39	0.47
Associate	3	45.67	7.57		
Relationship Associate	4	60.25	9.91		
Customer Associate	8	64.63	6.97		
Deputy Manager	2	50.00	1.41		
Officer	8	66.25	10.62		
JMG/S-1	2	49.00	7.07		
Manager	5	61.40	8.23		
SWO 'A'	3	59.67	11.02		
Officer assistant	3	72.33	7.10		
Business Development Executive	4	60.50	1.92		
Total	50	61.04	10.67		

There is no significant difference between the position name of the respondent and their job performance, $F(10, 39) = 2.111, p > .05$. Hence, H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected.

Therefore, the job performance of bank employees in all positions are same.

6. Implications of the study

This study imparts constructive insights into the scope of HR practices. It also analysed the literature regarding HR practices and job performance. It also aims at contributing a study toward human resource practices with respect to the job performance. The study on job performances resulted in identifying the various important aspects of HR practices, each of which is playing a significant role in understanding the relationship between job performance and HR. It is of paramount importance for the managers to understand the effect of HR practices on the job performance.

7. Suggestions

- Motivational training programme should be organized for employees to develop motivational trait.
- HR training such as technical training, quality training, life skills training, soft skills training and legal training are essential, so every bank should implement it.
- Banks should launch effective educational programme for the employees in order that they will simply tackle the challenging state of affairs of operating environments.
- Bank should build new policies to boost employee's participation at middle control level and prime level management.

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8. Conclusion

This study concluded that the male and female bank employee's job performance is same. The job performance level is same for all employees with respect to their residence, job orientation, types of bank, department and position. Whereas the job performance is differing among bank employees based on their educational qualification. It can be deciphered from this study, the importance of job performance in banking sector and the requirement of HRM practices to promote the employees performance effectively and efficiently. Job performance of an employee is the outcome of an employee towards her/his job. The employees' job performance outcome will depend on the various aspects of HR practices and other significant factors influencing the organisation. Focusing more on the job performance and analysing both qualitatively and quantitatively would bring more insight and enhances job performance at all levels of employment and as well as in career development. The further study can be conducted to identify the relationship of job performance with other variables such as stress, job satisfaction, absenteeism, turn over intention.